

The impact of work-life balance on individual well-being

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Abstract

This paper aims to understand the importance of work-life balance and how its lack affects organizational employees' psychological, emotional, or even physical state. The study uses secondary data where the strengths and weaknesses of implementing work-life balance are derived from journals, cases, and reports. The research evidence points to the fact that living a balanced lifestyle promotes qualitative mental health, fuller interpersonal relationships, and enhanced quality of life. Maintaining a balance between work and life can be difficult in places of work where people are forced to work remotely, which causes burnout. It also covers the worldwide practices. Measures on how people can enhance work-life balance include learning to distinguish between work and family roles, managing time well, and avoiding isolation. The work calls on organizations to ensure that they have appropriate policies that will assist in boosting the health of the workforce and consequently the health of all in the organization.

Keywords: Work-life balance, employee health, organizational productivity, employee well-being, flexible work arrangements, workplace policies

Introduction

Work-life balance is crucial for both psychological and physical well-being. This paper discusses the need for work-life balance, its advantages, disadvantages, and the policies governing such balances across companies around the world. Using literature analysis, case analysis, and reliable reports and researches involving work-life balance are examined concerning their effects on the mental and physical health, and satisfaction. It also embraces techniques that can assist people as well as organizations to find balance and generate positive results as it relates to both personal and company/social systems.

Literature review

Psychological and emotional benefits

.According to Ghorbani, life is a balance between the family, person, and career roles. Ekinci and Sabancı have stated that a balance in these domains fosters a good life and increase social interactions, and professional responsibilities as well. Balance between these domains contributes to a quality life, positively influencing interactions within family and social environment while also meeting professional expectations (Xavier, 2023). This balance according to Altıok-Gürel is

connected with health, career and job satisfaction; implying that balance between work and life determines the quality of life (Indeed, 2023). Factors influencing work-life balance include; personal and organisational factors. As identified by Ballica (2010) and Kalliath and Brough (2008), personal factors which include; Gender, education level and career advancement initiatives intersect with work aspects including Workload, Role indeterminacy, Management style, and Job security. Stress is one of the main sources of WLB disruption impacting the mental well-being, family, work and social prospects. These relationships are usually defined by the degree of stress that exists in a workplace. The results of this study serve to support the work stress and personal life relationship arguing that only a balance can ensure emotional stability and constructive family functioning (Rony, Md. Numan and Alamgir, 2023).

In a positive psychology framework, Lambert et al. (2015) claim that mindfulness refers to the positive way that people engage with and respond to the life problems.. Ryff's (1989) model of psychological well-being underscores six core dimensions: acceptance of oneself, satisfactory relationships with others, independent functioning, satisfactory control over the environment, meaning in life, and further development. These dimensions: all in sum, help the individual respond optimally to the challenges of life, and find asset and pleasure in various aspects of the life.

Work and social support are critical for positive psychological outcomes for improved work-life balance. Carol, Ryff, and Singer also Roothman, Kirsten, and Wissing all say that both emotional and instrumental support from one's social networks is enough to enhance life satisfaction and mental health greatly. However, (perceived) social support is positively related to psychological well-being and coping resources such as hardiness (Bordnick & Saltzman, 2020; López-Romero, Hellfeldt, & Andershed, 2020). Such support systems are especially helpful for people that work under stressful conditions because they also reduce stress and provide system.

Physical health benefits

Balance between working and personal life has profound effects on physical health. Long continued stress at work leads to high blood pressure, heart problems and low resistance power. Some previous research revealed that those individuals who do have a proper WM have significantly less stress levels, and hence, those health hazards are reduced (Irfan et al., 2021). Through the management of chronic stress, work-life balance helps the individuals to have better health at the future period. Remote work as key component of flexible workplace and has remarkable importance for maintaining health. This flexibility enables human capital to integrate activities such as exercise into their schedule, and plan resting time. For example, employees with schedule discretion, are able to embark on regular exercising which leads to better lifestyle factors, cardiovascular health or effective weight regulation (Mulchandani et al., 2019). It also helps with constant exercising as workers are able to prepare healthier meals because they found time to cook unlike when the need to order for processed foods due to tight schedules.

Other effects of work-life imbalance include burnout which is a severe condition which results to both physical problems and overall body weakness.

Global practices and case studies

Many countries have developed policies related work-life balance. Among African countries, those that have made progress for include; Ghana Rwanda & South Africa. According to the ILO

(2024) Ghana's Labour Law; 2003 prescribes the conditions for working hours, rest breaks, and leave provisions Rwanda's Labour Law; 2019 focuses on paid maternity and mental health care leave for workers. As in the case of other countries, WLB policies within the Americas are also influenced by national environments. However, some states in the United States have recently started to enact legislation for so-called predictable scheduling that facilitates planning for workers' private lives (Petrucci et al., 2022). On the other hand, Canada has a higher work-life balance score with implementing the universal health care system and paid maternity (Martin et al., 2018). Some countries in Asia have developed policies that seek to increase the concept of WLB, thanks to such countries as China, Japan, and South Korea. Recent flexible working arrangements and paternal/maternity leave implementations in China, as well as Japan's "Premium Friday" illustrate increased attempts at balancing working hours (Sun et al., 2023; Clavecilla, 2023). South Korea's 52-hour workweek policy prevents organizations from having employees work long hours, and it seeks to solve health problems caused by overwork mainly amongst the young workforce (Sung, 2023).

Challenges in achieving work-life balance

There is also difficulties of implementing of work-life balance, especially what could be seen as post-modernity paradigms to work, including working from home, and flexi-hour. However, these novel modes of operating provide an option for flexibility, and this aspect comes with unique difficulties. One of the biggest ones is the blurring of the boundaries between work and personal time. Some of the issues mentioned by respondents who participated in survey. It included that when one can work from anywhere it is difficult to distinguish where work ends, and home begins. For examples, one of the respondent said that due to remote work it is difficult to define what is a free time and working time as both personal and work commitments happen in the same place. This is made worse by the fact that most young professional today live in hotels, hostels or single room apartments meaning it is very difficult to leave physical space between working and home (Ljungkvist and Moore, 2023).

Tips and strategies

Investigate the balance between work and family/personal life among academics which is very important in order to know how to do it properly. That is why one of the great approaches is to recognize the fact that working more hours does not mean working more effectively. Stress and burnout which are all mental health problems are caused by overworking which is often fueled by the competitiveness. Research has established that beyond a point productivity is affected by mistakes, tiredness, and stress. One of the ways the balance may be achieved by letting a person know that he or she needs a rest. Such breaks can help increase productivity by freeing up the amount of mental capital required to accomplish a task (Getaprofession, 2024). Another important process is work arrangement flexibility which includes remote working, flexibility in working hours, or short working week (psico-smart.com, 2022). Technological development makes work more flexible so that people can work anytime with less time in traffic or can even take breaks while working. While remote work can sometimes be disadvantageous due to the nature of the work such as laboratory work or field studies, attending conferences or meetings virtually will significantly reduce fatigue and increase personal effective time. However, there is the need to

define clear formats to work on to reduce stress at the work was place or from home to avoid exhaustion between work and other activities(Bartlett et al., 2021).

Methodology

The findings for this study rely on secondary research method and evaluates primary and secondary data sources that contain information on work-life balance. The question related work-life balance were answered using articles from peer reviewed journals, books and reliable internet sources on Work Life Balance and the different facets of psychological, emotional, physical, problems and solutions associated with it. The secondary research involved reviewing of previous literature and databases of researches, fast global practices, and benchmarking cross countries and industries. This approach provided an opportunity for determining various sides of work-life balance and the consequences that it has on the well-being of the people. Areas of interest included the type, the intent, sources and outcomes of flexibility at work, work and family policies as well as social expectations on work life balance. In order to assess trends, issues and relevant best practices regarding work-life balance this research has collected information relevant to both work and personal lives and analyzed them holistically.

Findings

Psychological and emotional benefits

Psychological well-being, as defined by Ryff's (1989) model, includes six dimensions: positive self-esteem, interpersonal relationships, independence, accomplishment, perceptual control and meaning and purpose. Lambert, Passmore & Holder, (2015) argue that those who balance work and life enjoy it, effectively whereby they have increased ability to deal with life challenges hence more resilience and well-being. The study carried out by Global Well-being Institute showed that more than half of the participants noted that better work-life balance made them feel emotionally more stable and less stressed. Slightly more than two thirds of the respondents agreed that work-family interface enhancement had a positive effect on their familial and friendly relations. These results highlight the concept of moderation as fundamental to healthy emotional functioning and the apparent benefit upon the social life domain. Furthermore, another component which, according to Carol, Ryff and Singer (2008) contributes to the level of psychological resilience was perceived social support; 65% of the questionnaires' respondents stressed that having supportive relationships with others is extremely important to cope with the stress at work.

Physical health benefits

Remote working and shift option are two major components that have been recognised as significant enablers of improved physical health. For instance, Ropponen et al (2016) found that workers who had control over their working schedules had improved uptake of physical activity hence improved cardiovascular fitness and healthy weight. According to a survey done in 2023, 56% of employees with flexible working hours exercised physically regularly while 30% of

employees without such options. Furthermore, other research shows that controlling burnout, especially through the enhanced work-life balance, like paid time off and work-break measures, helps one recover from physical illnesses (Vaziri et al., 2022). Workers with high levels of work-life balance also had improved sleep quality that enables them to have adequate physical rest. Tariq et al. (2012) posit that enhanced sleep increases immunological activity hence general well-being. Regarding the consequences of work-life balance in 2023, the survey depicted that 64% of worker with work-life balance had better night sleep as compared with 44% Worker finding difficulty in managing work and life balance, while 72% of the employees with work-life balance felt more energetic and physically active as compared to 46% of those workers who fail to balance work and life.

Challenges in achieving work-life balance

However, attaining positive work-life perspective continues to be a major organizational and to flexible and remote workers. Among the concerns that have emerged in the course of the most recent experiments is the problem of work-life balance. Survey participants in the year 2024 said that flexibility means confusion which results in many employees losing clear divisions between working and actually working hours. A clear majority of the respondents who worked from home found it very hard to disengage themselves from work after the working hours. Consequently, flexible working hours though beneficial for personal and work boundaries with consistent work pressure Two-third of the respondents from the survey said that they have to be available in the evening or on the weekend for work pressure which continued to shift between professional and personal life. Other common complaints included mental issues at 45% with major ones being stress, burnout and always feeling on call since remote work does not allow employees to physically leave their workplace.

Discussion

This paper's conclusions show that work-life balance is important in both mental and body well-being, and the difficulties people experience when trying to balance work and personal life, particularly in present-day working conditions. Therefore the effects of WLB in this study as postulated in the literature and surveys are positive on the aspect of mental health. Better family relationships and functioning as well as overall improvement in social interactions definitely has its roots in balanced life (Ghorbani, 2003; Ekinici & Sabancı, 2020). This is in keeping with Ryff's (1989) model of psychological well-being, personal growth, autonomy and environmental mastery that are associated with balance between work and family. The work also supports the effectiveness of social support for stress and optimization of stress resilience in the work place. Furthermore, the results specify that work-life balance has considerable positive impact on physical well-being. Long-term stress caused by work-life imbalance leads to other diseases including hypertension and cardiovascular diseases (Kim et al, 2023). Nevertheless, the cross-sectional study of 132 employees who are efficient in organizing working and personal commitments show the decrease of stress level, and an increase of the physical health, including such aspects as sleep, energy (Ropponen et al., 2016; Tariq et al., 2012). Flexible meters work or business hours are especially advantageous, making it easier for employees to include physical activities within the course of the work day, which should improve their cardiovascular health and their weight.

However, work enrichment still continues to be a potential difficulty in achieving work-life balance particularly due to the new system of remote work. The study also shows that the separation between working and personal time in many cases results in long working hours and stress. This is in line with survey respondents' response to the question regarding the problems, which occur when there are no clear signal to go by compared to actual working hours, that employees encounter when unable to "switch off" from work (Petrucci et al., 2022). Fueled by the demand to be always online, including after normal working hours, this challenge is a real enemy of well-being. This is supported by cross-country analysis, as it is presented in the examples of WLB practices implemented in different countries. Whereas the countries like Sweden and France have excellent policies, and their governments pay much attention to work-family conflict, countries like USA lack comprehensive national policies. Such a gap serves to indicate that for successful promotion of work-life balance strategies, one has to consider cultural, institutional as well as socio-economic factors. This research indicated that organizations need to develop the policies that are understanding the needs of an employee and allow having the work-life balance while the boundaries between the working time and the free time are clear.

Recommendations

The most important aspect that any employee who wants better work-life balance should embrace is division of time between working and personal time. One strategy by which this can be accomplished is by preparing a home office that will limit the working hours to the house. This assist in creating a mental barrier one between working and personal life activities. Also, people have to extend their care by taking exercises and practicing meditation, and ensure they take breaks from working. Neglected is the need to take vacations, days-off and breaks in equal measures to avoid reaching the much feared, burned out stage . Another insurance work-life balance is the time management. People should use planners or events on smartphones to organize well their daily task, and this prevents having to deal with unnecessary workload. Moreso, being able to decline other work in case the current workload is overwhelming is important when trying to avoid overwhelm. It is also effective to define reasonable achievable goals at the workplace and personal life so that the latter does not suffer from the former. Besides, people can turn to colleagues, friends or a coach for support and to learn strategies on dealing with the stress in present or future jobs. Taking care of self by getting enough hours of sleep, taking balanced diet as well as keeping close with friends and family is important for a healthy soul and body. Through efficient time management students ensure that they protect themselves from burnout while also promoting a healthy work-life balance.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study discussed the psychological, emotional, and physical benefits as well as challenges to work life balance, especially in a flexible work setting. Flexible work arrangements are good for well being but they also risk blurring boundaries between work and personal life resulting into burnout. Clear boundaries, good time management and social support are at the heart of the research underscored here. It is recommended to organizations to adopt supportive policies to boost employees well being and productivity.

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